

Mapping Indoor air quality vulnerability across England and Wales: A neighbourhood classification of exposure for England and Wales

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Summary

This paper outlines the first part of the project investigating the population's vulnerability to indoor air pollution. It investigates and maps the sources of indoor air pollution across England and Wales using various secondary data sources. It then uses composite scores and cluster analysis to provide useful outputs and insight into the distribution of the air pollution sources. This research is intended to enable discussions on spatial justice, social inequalities, and human vulnerabilities in the ambient environment, and provide insight into gaps in indoor air quality research.

KEYWORDS: Indoor Air Quality, Spatial Inequalities, Cluster analysis, urban analytics, Ambient environment

1. Introduction & background

Indoor air pollution is a substantial global health burden increasingly recognised as an issue of environmental and social justice (Pillariseti et al., 2022). Indoor air pollution refers to a variety of airborne pollutants, including dampness and mould, chemicals in materials and sprays, or pollutants from the combustion of solid fuels and human activity. Both exposure to poor-quality ambient environments and vulnerability to adverse effects on health and well-being are unevenly distributed, socially and spatially (Boeing et al., 2023).

Despite people in the Global North typically spending an estimated 80-90% of their time indoors, socio-spatial inequalities in indoor environmental quality are relatively poorly understood (Spiru and Simona, 2017; Ferguson et al., 2021). Nevertheless, the understanding of indoor air pollution, its adverse effect on human health and its relations to socio-spatial factors is understudied in UK even though it has been known that outdoor air pollution contributes to 28,000-36,000 premature deaths each year (Ferguson et al., 2021).

We aim to improve our understanding of the complex socio-spatial drivers of vulnerability to poor IAQ by mapping the exposure to sources of indoor air pollution across England and Wales. We do this in four steps. First, we identify sources of indoor air pollution through relevant literature and its critical review. Second, we collect relevant secondary data from open sources. Third, we use composite score-building and cluster analysis to reduce the dimensions of the data and search for common patterns. Fourth, we build an interactive map with the outputs using ArcGIS online to allow the general public, policy-makers and any stakeholders to with easy access.

2. Methods & Data,

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To provide a somewhat clearer overview of likely drivers of exposure to poor IAQ, we build on Pourkiaei and Romain (2023) grouping IAQ drivers into three categories related to: outdoor environment; building characteristics; and indoor conditions. We find this generalization useful and expand it in **Figure 1**, dividing IAQ drivers into three groups; environmental, structural and human. Environmental sources relate to the outdoor environment of the dwelling; structural are those from the structure of the dwelling, whether surfaces or the building itself; and human sources originate from people’s activities in the home.

Figure 1 Break down of indoor air quality drivers

To date, there is no publicly available dataset of socio-spatial variation to poor IAQ in households across England and Wales. Some data on household perceptions of indoor environmental quality are available from the English Housing Survey (2023) however, these are not sufficient for mapping or modelling IAQ spatially. Nevertheless, other publicly available secondary data sets can be used to infer vulnerability to poor IAQ, which is a similar approach to well-established indices of deprivation (IMD, 2016) and social vulnerability (Cutter and Finch, 2008), where a collection of carefully selected influential variables are used to derive information about the likely distribution of deprivation or vulnerability at a neighbourhood scale.

We collect relevant secondary data for each dimension identified in our literature review: the outdoor environment, structure of the house, and human activity (Figure 1). We make use of public sources such as the National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory (NAEI, 2021), Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) (DLUHC, 2024), Census 2021 (ONS, 2021) and information on population smoking from the Office for National Statistics (ONS, 2022). Additionally, we combine Census information with EPCs to derive a measure of population floor-space density to represent indoor crowding.

While there are multiple methods suitable for composite score-building, the lack of comprehensive granular data on indoor air quality does not allow for ground-truth comparison or for weighting to be used. Thus we remain loyal to the traditional method of unweighted composite score given by equation 1, where composite score CS is the summation of composite variables $CV_1 \dots CV_n$. given each composite variable is normalised, standardised and divided into deciles to create consistent scoring.

$$CS = CV_1 + CV_2 + CV_3 + \dots CV_n \quad (1)$$

We derive three indices of indoor air quality vulnerability: environmental, structural and human, which can be observed separately on the final outputs. We then use an agglomerative hierarchical clustering algorithm to identify distinctive IAQ patterns. The indices present patterns often spatially related to the level of urbanity, therefore, we also incorporate the Urban/Rural classification (ONS, 2011) from the latest Census into the cluster analysis.

3. Results & Discussion

We identify seven groups of areas (**Figure 2**), each with a distinctive combination of indoor air quality vulnerability dimensions. Distinctive geographies emerge for each dimension of exposure: where the similarity between human and environmental dimensions exists, structural dimensions often show an opposing pattern. The importance of urban typologies for indoor air pollution is captured in four of our cluster types.

The most overwhelmingly urban cluster type (99% of LSOA classified as urban) is the “Urban extreme of environment and human vulnerability” (C3). These neighbourhoods have the highest levels of vulnerability across human and to a lesser extent environmental, dimensions. Here, IAQ is likely to be poorer owing to a range of population-related vulnerability factors, that have structural drivers, including overcrowding, renting, or deprivation. A group of areas labelled as “Urban lows” (C1) experience very little vulnerability across all dimensions. Still predominantly urban (94% of LSOA), these areas concentrate spatially are likely relatively affluent suburbs, made up of larger and owner-occupied properties, where outdoor pollutants are comparatively low. The most rural cluster “Urban-Rural extreme of housing vulnerability” (C4) (51% of LSOAs are urban) has the highest housing vulnerability of any cluster, but the lowest environment and human-based vulnerability. The cluster concentrates in rural areas where solid-walled properties concentrate, often challenging to heat and prone to dampness. Rural areas are more likely to be off the gas grid, necessitating solid fuels that promote indoor air pollution, including coal or wood (Roberts, 2020).

Figure 2 Indoor Air Quality Vulnerability Clusters for England and Wales

These clusters show an uneven distribution of indoor air quality sources across the neighbourhoods in England and Wales. While some levels of inequalities within the urban environments should be expected (Sarkar et al., 2024), some could be mitigated through policies and local council improvement plans. Most importantly, investigating the dimensions separately along with the clusters shows that different neighbourhoods might require different ways to control for better indoor air quality. Outdoor air improvements are very helpful in improving the indoor air quality in densely populated urban areas. However, support for housing improvement and the availability of cleaner energy might be needed more in rural areas.

Characterising areas based on indoor air quality indices and identifying areas with similar characteristics has three-fold benefits. First, it provides a simple and understandable way of classifying vulnerability to poor indoor air quality at national and local levels for policy-makers. Second, it offers a way to compare differences between neighbourhoods, local authorities and regions to underpin decision-making and resource allocation to address poor indoor air quality. Third, it offers a benchmark for further quantitative research on indoor air quality. Nevertheless, there are a number of limitations. Firstly, each of the data sources has its own caveats. The latest census has been collected during a pandemic which means some population data can be inaccurate. The radon data set (British Geological Survey, 2022) is created by sample collection based on individual household demands, meaning the data is more accurate in areas where people worry more about radon exposure. Furthermore, the EPC data set is an incomplete set capturing between 50% to 80% of all properties in LSOAs across England and Wales. While future work should investigate these limitations in further detail and explore the possibility of data imputation and correction, it is important to note that improvements to data collection will be necessary to more accurately represent the indoor air quality vulnerabilities.

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Biographies

Lenka Hasova is a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Bristol, where she recently completed her PhD in Human Geography as part of the Quantitative Spatial Science Research Group. Lenka researches and teaches widely across Geographic Data Science techniques. Her PhD research focuses on concepts and applications of spatial interaction models as networks.

Caitlin Robinson is an Senior Academic Fellow and Senior Proleptic Lecturer at the University of

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Lin Zhang is a postdoctoral researcher at the University of Manchester. Lin is interested in energy geographies and applying quantitative and qualitative techniques to understand the social and spatial distribution of energy poverty. Lin completed her PhD at the University of Leeds exploring energy poverty in the context of China.